

DIAGNOSTIC AND TREATMENT EXPERIENCE (IN THE CASE OF RAT LICE INFECTION IN PETS)

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Abstract: *Violations of zoohygienic standards for keeping animals in pet shops and pet stores create the necessary conditions for the widespread spread of invasive and infectious diseases, including pet rats. In this regard, there is a need to develop systemic etiotropic therapy for lice infestation in house rats. About 3.7% of the rats referred to the veterinarian were found to be infested with lice, their diagnosis was based on a specific clinical appearance and macro- or microscopic detection of this parasite. Treatment of rats with the delcid insecticide drug, according to the scheme presented in the work, allows to reliably rid the animal of a certain parasitic disease and is recommended by veterinarians for use in practical practice. An analysis of the most likely sources of infestation of pet rats with lice of the genus *Polyplax spinulosa* was also carried out.*

Key words: *house rats, lice, *Polyplax spinulosa*, ectoparasites, invasion, Deltcid, insects.*

The pet decorative rat (*Rattus norvegicus domestica*) is a domestic subspecies of the common gray rat, and they are becoming more and more popular as pets every year. Due to their small size, relatively low capriciousness, simple growth and feeding conditions, rats have shown themselves to be an excellent animal for keeping apartments. Most of the animals go to the veterinarian because of invasive diseases. Parasitic types of arthropods (ticks, fleas, lice) cause the development of a pathological process in the host organism as a result of their direct life and infection with pathogens of dangerous infectious diseases. Lice of the species *Polyplax spinulosa* are ectoparasites of rats, including decorative pets. The first information

on the circulation of this insect in the rodent population of our region was published by Sosina (1970), but due to the complexity of the biological cycle, the prevention and treatment of infestation still causes difficulties

The object of the study was pet decorative rats, which had signs of lice infestation. The diagnosis was made based on the results of macroscopic examination of ectoparasites under a magnifying glass and microscopic detection of lice nits [1,3,5]. For microscopic examination, a small amount of rat hair was selected at the border, exposed and unaffected areas were placed on a slide, fixed with immersion oil. The obtained samples were examined under the low magnification of a binocular microscope.

The clinical condition of the animal was evaluated based on examinations. Delcid (Delcid) based on synthetic pyrethroid deltamethrin was used as a means of etiotropic therapy. The positive dynamics and effectiveness of the selected drug were determined by the results of repeated administration of animals in the veterinary clinic. Delcid was chosen by us because it is an inexpensive and relatively budgetary insectocidal agent, which has proven itself well in clinical practice in the treatment of ectoparasites in rabbits. 0.5 ml of this drug was dissolved in 1500 ml of warm water (up to 25 ° C), the resulting solution was applied liberally to a cotton pad, and the entire coat of the rat was treated. The animal was wrapped in a towel and was not allowed to lick for 3-5 minutes. The described manipulations were carried out two and three times between 7 days (second treatment) and 14 days (third treatment), depending on the presence of clinical signs in the animal.

Clinical signs such as itching (moderately periodic to constant), areas of alopecia with hyperemia of the skin in various regions of the body, and excoriation zones with dried epithelial shell and blood were found in the studied individuals, and general oppression was noted in some rats. Adults (adult) lice are described by us as light brown moving dots on the skin, and nits (eggs) are in the form of small whitish

balls on the hair, most owners describe this phenomenon as "dandruff". The appearance of polyplax spinulosa eggs found during the work is presented in Fig. 1.

Figure 1 - Egg (nit) louse Polyplax spinulosa

Thus, six rats needed two treatments with the drug, one rat was treated three times, another rat died due to mycoplasma infection, which complicated the disease under study.

From the start of therapy to the disappearance of clinical signs ("recovery") was longer (15-24 days) in rats with severe escoriosis than in rats with mild skin damage (up to 9 days).

An important step in our research was to identify the original source of the lice, Polyplax spinulosa, which caused the development of this disease. Based on anamnestic data, we formulated four categories of presumed insect sources. Three out of eight rats (37%) were purchased from the kennel shortly before the development of clinical signs of infestation by life cycle analysis. The outcome of the disease and the number of treatments in the studied subjects are presented in Table 1.

№	Age	Clinical signs	Outcome of the disease	Number of treatments
1	1 month	itching, lice eggs on hairs, adults and nymphs on skin	recovery on day 9	2

2	2 months	severe itching, crusts, lice eggs on hairs, adults and nymphs on the skin	recovery on the 15th day	2
3	9 months	excoriations with crusts/blood, intermittent severe itching, oppression	recovery for 24 days	3
4	1 month	runny nose, mucous discharge from the eyes, itching, alopecia, depression	recovery for 4 days	one
5	20 months	severe itching, excoriations with crusts/blood, hairy lice eggs, lethargy	recovery on the 19th day	2
6	3 weeks	itching, lice eggs on the hairs, adults and nymphs on the skin in	recovery on the 8th day	2
7	3 weeks	itching, lice eggs on hairs, adults and nymphs on skin	recovery on the 7th day	2
5	16 months	itching, excoriations with crusts/blood, lice eggs on hairs, adults and nymphs on skin	recovery on the 17th day	2

Also, one rat (13%) was purchased at a pet store, where a large number of relatives of the same age were kept in questionable zoohygienic conditions. The development of the disease in two people (25%) occurred after contact with other rats, in this case it was the direct source of the imaginary stages of the louse, but it should be noted that one of the sick animals had reduced immunity due to

mycoplasma infection. In the other two animals, parasite infestation was observed after changing the litter material (sawdust) and hay used in maintenance, but the presence of lice in these materials could not be reliably proven. The percentage of parasite sources listed is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3 - Ratio of possible sources of Polyplax spinulosa

Summary. Based on the above data, it should be concluded that in 3.7% of the rats referred to the veterinarian, it is possible to determine the infection with lice of the genus Polyplax spinulosa, the diagnosis should be confirmed by the presence of the parasite or the imaginary form of eggs (nits).

Of the 8 rats studied in 7 animals, the drug Delcid reliably demonstrated an insecticidal effect sufficient to completely eliminate all lice, as indicated by the absence of itching, excoriation and other external signs of infestation. It's done. The treatment regimen and dosage of the drug shown in the work can be used by veterinarians in the treatment of rats with this pathology. It should also be noted that the period of freeing the animal from lice and restoring normal life is directly related to the level of development of clinical symptoms - in rats with little or no skin damage, this period is limited to 9 days, which means strong scratching and skin integrity 50% shorter than nonviolent rats. Also, during research, we have identified

the main sources of infestation of rats with *Polyplax spinulosa* lice, which include the kennel or pet store where the animal was purchased, other rats in contact with the animal, litter material (sawdust), and hay.

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